

M44 Cluster Distance Calculation Using Distance Modulus and GAIA EDR3 Data

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ABSTRACT

The open clusters M45 and M44 have been very well studied and a lot of data can be acquired for both clusters. Using data from the GAIA EDR3 release, we created a Color-Magnitude Diagram (CM) of the M45 cluster’s absolute magnitudes. This diagram was used as a standard to compare to a CM of the apparent magnitudes of the open cluster M44. Using trend lines, the distance modulus of the M44 CM was compared to the standardized M45 CM to calculate a value for M44’s distance in parsecs. The results yielded a -6.24% error, likely due to imperfections in subset selections, parallax measurements, and averaging.

1. INTRODUCTION

As a well-studied open cluster, M45 (also known, commonly, as the Pleiades) is very luminous and close, with a right ascension of 3h 47m 24s and declination of +24°, 7’, 0” . Similarly, M44 (also known as the Beehive Cluster) is another popular Messier-Catalogue open cluster with a right ascension of 8h 40m 24s and declination of +19°, 59’, 0” . While both clusters already have multiple measurements of their distances, we will be using the distance modulus relationship:

$$m - M = -5 + 5 * \log_{10}(d_{pc})$$

This relationship will give a calculation for the distance to M44 given the correct parameters.

The programs that we will be using are TOPCAT for the extraction and visualization of GAIA data, and Excel for the manipulation and evaluation of the data.

2. PROCEDURE

2.1. Creating a Standard CM

We will be using the GAIA data for the M45 region to create a standard CM graph. First, using TOPCAT’s cone search function, a 1° cone around M45’s RA and Dec provides 27,087 entries. Each entry contains extensive data on many attributes of the star, however, for our purposes, we will be focusing mainly on *ra* (Right Ascension), *dec* (Declination), *pmra* (Proper Motion Right

Figure 1. Sky Plot of M45 region

Ascension), *pmdec* (Proper Motion Declination), *parallax*, *phot_g_mean_mag* (Apparent Magnitude), and *bp_rp* (Blue-Red Color Index).

The table we now have contains all GAIA-registered objects within that 1° cone of the sky (see Figure 1). It is obvious that not all of the stars mapped in this region are a part of M45, and therefore we must narrow our selection. We attempted to create a subset of only M45 member stars by graphing the *pmra* and *pmdec* to find a grouping of similar motion vectors.

From this plane plot, a new subset was manually drawn around a densely packed region away from the center of the graph (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Sky plot of $pmra$ vs. $pmdec$. M45 subset in blue.

Figure 3. Plane plot of $pmra$ vs $pmdec$. M45 subset in blue.

This new subset narrowed our selection to 490 entries, presumably all in M45. A new boolean was created for the entire table to delineate if each entry was inside this subset.

To create a standard CM graph, we needed to calculate the absolute magnitudes of each star given their parallax and apparent magnitude. To get an approximate value for the parallax, a histogram of the M45 subset was created with the $parallax$ parameter (see Figure 4). This graph yielded an estimated median value of 7.389 mas. Using the parallax-distance formula, we calculated an estimate for the distance to M45:

$$d_{M45} = \frac{1}{p_{as}}$$

$$d_{M45} = \frac{1000}{p_{mas}}$$

Figure 4. Histogram graph of $parallax$ of the M45 subset. The median value was determined to be 7.389 mas.

Figure 5. Standard CM Graph using M45 subset.

$$d_{M45} = \frac{1000}{7.389_{mas}} = 135.34_{pc}$$

The M45 subset table was then exported to Excel to create an equation for the absolute magnitude. Using GAIA data for the apparent magnitudes, ($phot_g_mean_mag$), and our calculated distance, 135.34 pc, the absolute value for each star could be calculated:

$$m - M = -5 + 5 * \log_{10}(d)$$

$$m = phot_g_mean_mag$$

$$d = 135.34_{pc}$$

$$M = m + 5 - 5 * \log_{10}(135.34_{pc})$$

After creating a new column, abs_mag , using this equation, the column was graphed in a scatter plot against the Blue-Red Color Index (bp_rp). With the bp_rp as the independent axis and the abs_mag as the dependent axis, after flipping the y-axis we created a CM graph to use as our standard CM (see Figure 5).

Figure 6. Plane plot of $pmra$ vs $pmdec$. M44 subset in blue.

Figure 7. Color-Magnitude Graphs of M45 and M44.

2.2. Creating M44 CM

After creating a standard CM, next, we had to create a CM graph of the apparent magnitude ($phot_g_mean_mag$) and bp_rp of the M44 cluster. To do this, many of the steps were repeated from 2.1. Again, the TOPCAT cone search function was used to retrieve 17,978 entries of stars within a 1° cone. Using the plane plot of $pmra$ vs. $pmdec$, a new M44 subset was manually drawn (see Figure 6). The $bprp$ and $phot_g_mean_mag$ data for this subset was exported to Excel to compare against the data for M45.

2.3. Calculating Distance Modulus

With both the M44 apparent magnitude graph and the M45 absolute magnitude graph, the data from each cluster was compared side-by-side (see Figure 7).

The vertical distance between these two plots yields $m - M$, also known as the distance modulus. Due to the extensive outliers in these data sets, we used two lines of best fit to measure this distance. Using Excel, a 6th order polynomial trend line was fitted to each graph,

Figure 8. Polynomial trend lines for M44 (in red) and M45 (in green) and $h(x)$ (in blue).

yielding formulas for M44 and M45 respectively:

$$f_{M44}(x) = -0.0643x^6 + .6663x^5 - 2.6177x^4 + 5.1179x^3 \dots$$

$$\dots - 6.1993x^2 + 8.825x + 5.6752$$

$$f_{M45}(x) = -.0647x^6 + 0.6879x^5 - 2.7841x^4 + 5.5115x^3 \dots$$

$$\dots - 6.2123x^2 + 7.823x + .3162$$

We then expressed the difference between M44 and M45 as the function $h(x)$. The mean value of this graph was then found by taking the integral between the lowest and highest M44 bp_rp values (see Figure 8):

$$h(x) = f_{M44}(x) - f_{M45}(x)$$

$$h(c) = m - M$$

$$m - M = \frac{\int_{0.020564556}^{3.905756} h(x) dx}{3.905756 - 0.020564556}$$

$$m - M = 6.1988$$

Finally, using the original distance modulus equation:

$$m - M = -5 + 5 * \log_{10}(d)$$

the distance can be calculated using our new value for the distance modulus:

$$\log(d_{M44}) = \frac{(m - M) + 5}{5}$$

$$\log(d_{M44}) = \frac{6.1988 + 5}{5}$$

$$d_{M44} = 173.68_{pc}$$

3. RESULTS

Our calculations yielded the distance to M44 as 173.68_{pc} . While this value seems reasonable, we compared it to traditionally accepted values for this object's distance. Using the SIMBAD Astronomical Database, we found the following distance values:

distance	unit	err-	err+
0.18	kpc		
0.186	kpc	-0.006	+0.006
183.0	pc		
186	pc	-0	+0
186	pc		
187	pc		
187	pc		

¹ We decided to compare our value to the mode of these values:

$$d_{M44} = 186_{pc}$$

and then calculated our percent error:

$$\%_{error} = \frac{173.68 - 186}{186} * 100$$

$$\%_{error} = -6.24\%$$

As our measured distance is lower than the accepted distance, our calculated distance modulus was too small. There are a few errors that could have led to this result.

First, the estimated median parallax value of the M45 data could have been too large, resulting in a smaller average absolute magnitude of the M45 CM plot and, therefore, a smaller distance modulus. This error is extremely likely as the estimation for the parallax was done visually using a cursor estimate.

Secondly, manually creating subsets for the M44 and M45 data entries is bound to be flawed as there will inevitably be stars in those regions that are not a part of those clusters. Because of this, some of the data for each graph will contain outlier values that could have shifted the trend lines and the distance modulus.

Finally, an error in our method of calculating the distance modulus could result in smaller distance estimates such as ours. This error seems likely given the different values for distance modulus' that come from different methods of measuring it.

Having a larger data set would make these errors more negligible, but is difficult due to the observational limits of these systems.

We also used the same parallax-distance relation as we used for M45 to check our distance value for M44. Using another histogram plot of the *parallax*, the estimated median value was 5.38_{mas} . Using the same method, we calculated the distance to M44:

$$d_{pc} = \frac{1000}{p_{mas}}$$

$$d_{pc} = \frac{1000}{5.38_{mas}}$$

$$d_{pc} = 186_{pc}$$

This method yielded a distance that matched the results from SIMBAD. Because of this, we can assume that errors within the M44 dataset are negligible, and it is errors within the M45 dataset and within our methods of measuring the distance modulus that yield us the smaller distance.

¹ NGC 2632, SIMBAD, <https://simbad.u-strasbg.fr/simbad/sim-id?mescat.distance=on&Ident=%401110595&Name=NGC++2632&submit=display+selected+measurements#lab%meas>.